

Ledor project: The role of the *ledor* (reader) of visually impaired candidates in job and universities admission exams

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Our research project intends to understand the role of the ledor (reader) of the visually impaired candidate in tests of job and universities admission exams. Such research would broaden the academy's understanding of the ledores's role in interacting with candidates during their tests, as well as helping to build mechanisms that make the participation of the visually impaired person in such processes more inclusive. This is an anti-deficiencialist perspective, which seeks to remove psychophysiological barriers from society, allowing people with disabilities to participate in selection/evaluation processes on a fair basis. The expected result from the work is the creation of an action protocol for ledores (readers), which assist visually impaired candidates in job and universities admission exams.

Introduction

Since the 2000s, there are laws that guarantee the right of people with disabilities to have priority service in several facilities in Brazil. In 2004, Decree No. 5.296/2004 regulated a previous legislation, specifying the services to which people with disabilities are entitled in various situations, among them the taking of job and universities admission examinations. Therefore, there is a look out for improvements in the task of meeting this right. One of the means that has been used involves the participation of a person, called *ledor* (reader), to read tests for the candidate who requests this service at the time of registration.

However, little is known about the interference that this actor exerts on the performance of the candidate's test. Therefore, this research will seek to understand in more depth the characteristics of this interaction, allowing a reflection on ways to improve this process and proposing actions to assist on this task.

To this end, a partnership was set between UNIFESP (Federal University of São Paulo) - Campus Diadema, UNESP (São Paulo State University) – Campus Rio Claro and VUNESP (Foundation for the Vestibular (Entrance Exam) of the São Paulo State University), a foundation that conducts job and universities admission exams, and assessments throughout Brazil, including the entrance exams for all UNESP and some UNIFESP courses, such as the medical course for example.

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The partnership

The beginning of this partnership took place in December 2017, when Renato Marcone was invited to VUNESP by Rodrigo Bortolucci to assist in a specific task: to discuss ways of adapting mathematical tests for a blind student on a specific exam.

After completing the task of thinking about mathematical tests adapted for candidates with visual impairment in general, Renato Marcone proposed that the collaborative experience did not end there, that it should become a research partnership between the two institutions they represented. The idea was well received by the board of VUNESP, as well as by the board of UNIFESP – Campus Diadema.

Theoretical basis

To build a theoretical basis to which we will focus to justify the research that we are proposing, we bring Renato Marcone's PhD research (2015), which was an effort to think about the dynamics of the relationship between the people with disabilities and the teaching and learning processes of mathematics. Marcone (2015) states that, since he started working with inclusion, he was always convinced that teaching mathematics to excluded people was something that would contribute to the autonomy of the society, and not only for the people with disability. As Paulo Freire (1996) taught, autonomy only makes sense when it is collective.

These arguments also apply to admission mechanisms, such as job and universities admission examinations, in the same way that they apply to assessment and evaluation mechanisms. They are almost invariably built by “normal” people for “normal” people. When *differences* arise seeking to participate in these selection and evaluation systems, the gap that exists between the desire to include and the ability to perform this inclusion in a satisfactory manner is evident.

Given this perspective, Marcone brought an analogy, at first, between the way the West sees the East, based on Edward Said's book, “Orientalism: the invention of the East by the West”, first published in 1978, and the way “Normal” people see, often inventing, the “Abnormal”, an analogy that gradually became theorizing, culminating in the creation of the concept: *deficiencialism*.

Deficiencialism would be the set of practices and networks of stereotypes that build a distorted view of people with disabilities as incapable of tasks, extrapolating the real limitation that the disability can cause in the person. For example, a blind person, who is unable to fly a plane with the technology currently available, is also stereotyped as a person who, consequently, will not be able to learn mathematics, as this is a very visual science (Marcone, 2010). The extrapolation of limitations is at the heart of what Marcone calls *deficiencialism* (for more, see Marcone (2015)). The following statement by Vygotsky (our translation) reinforces what Marcone has been saying:

The whole apparatus of human culture (of the external form of behaviour) is adapted to the person's normal psychophysiological organization. Our entire culture is calculated for the person with certain organs - hand, eye, ear - and certain brain functions. All our instruments, all the technique, all the signs and symbols are calculated for a normal type of person. And from here comes that illusion of convergence, of natural passage from natural to cultural forms, which, in fact, is not possible due to the very nature of things and which we try to reveal in their true content (Vygotsky, 2011, p. 5).

Still in his PhD dissertation, Marcone proposes an *anti-deficiencialist* attitude towards barriers arising from the psychophysiological organization of society in general. Then, this research presents itself as an *anti-deficiencialism* attitude, seeking to interfere in the job and universities admission examinations in Brazil, while proposing to build mechanisms that could overcome such barriers instead of only criticizing them.

Research Aim

This research aims to understand how the role of the *ledor* (reader) influences candidates with visual impairment and based on this understanding, to think of alternatives that can improve the relationship of the *ledor* with the candidate with visual impairment. As a secondary objective, this research intends, in the end, to propose an action protocol for *ledores* who work in tests assisting visually impaired candidates, as well as thinking about a digital solution, such as a software or a special device.

Methodology and evolution so far

Because of the new coronavirus pandemic, our research changed its course drastically. Instead of face-to-face interviews and pilot assessments with visual impaired volunteers, we are analysing audio recordings of the candidates taking their tests aided by a *ledor*. VUNESP records, in audio, all the tests where there is the aid of a *ledor*, as a standard, and it is these recordings that we are having access and analysing, to understand the interferences of the *ledor*.

All the participants of this research are 18 or more in age and have agreed to giving us access to their recordings, by signing an Informed Consent Form (ICF), created by us, which is provided by VUNESP, online, during the registration process for any admission examination, through their own website. Also, our research has been approved by an independent Ethics Committee in Brazil.

Preliminary data provided by VUNESP in 2018 showed that they received an average number of 150 requests per year for a *ledor*, including all the assessments and job and universities admission examinations they organized from 2012 to 2017. We got the permission to access all the authorised audio recordings of 2020. Our expectation was to receive, at least, 10 authorizations, to perform a relevant analysis. The average time of each audio is 7 hours, because the visually impaired students have the right of an extended time to perform their exams in Brazil. However, early January 2021, we have got the consolidated data: until October 2020, we had 321 authorizations from candidates who signed the ICF.

Then, our first decision was to classify those candidates in two groups: job admission candidates and university admission candidates and we started looking into the first group.

The authorizations referring to job admission examinations are a total of 167. Of that number, 58 registrations were not confirmed (some due to the suspension of the admission exam because of the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, others because some lack of documents, etc.), 24 were absent and 84 showed to take their test. Among the 84, we have 72 audios available (sometimes the candidate releases the *ledor* at the moment of the test and audio is not recorded). Then, we have, potentially, 500 hours of audio recordings to analyse.

At this point, we are facing the challenge of: how to treat all this data to reach our research goal, without giving up the qualitative character of the research?

Last comments

Once we saw the huge amount of data, our first reaction was joy, because this is a clear sign that students with disability are fighting their way towards a public job or a seat in a university.

After the first feeling of rejoice, we felt very worried. We have in front of us a unique opportunity to make some change on the exclusionist processes that were consolidated for so many years in Brazil, helping to create a more inclusive environment on the job and universities admission examinations.

Hence, we are at a place where we are seeking how to use those data in the wisest way, and for that, we count on the MES colleagues' support to design our next step.

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